

Astrovirus.MLB1

Megavirus.chiliensis

200
150
100
50
0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Wuhan.insect.virus.23

6000
4000
2000
0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Hubei.picorna.like.virus.62

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Zygocactus.virus.X

900
600
300
0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Hubei.picorna.like.virus.63

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Carnation.mottle.virus

8000

6000

4000

2000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Youcai.mosaic.virus

4000

3000

2000

1000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Klebsiella.virus.Miro

600
400
200
0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

uncultured.crAssphage

150000

100000

50000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Klebsiella.virus.KP27

400
300
200
100
0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Acinetobacter.phage.Acj61

1000

500

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Pitaya.virus.X

6000

4000

2000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Pandoravirus.inopinatum

40
20
0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Tobacco.mosaic.virus

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Klebsiella.virus.PMBT1

300
200
100
0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Pseudomonas.phage.201phi2.1

600

400

200

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Cactus.virus.X

10000

7500

5000

2500

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Hubei.picorna.like.virus.61

Paprika.mild.mottle.virus

4000
3000
2000
1000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Bell.pepper.mottle.virus

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Microbacterium.phage.Burro

150
100
50
0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Pseudomonas.virus.PspYZU08

2000

1500

1000

500

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Tomato.mosaic.virus

4e+05
3e+05
2e+05
1e+05
0e+00

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Rehmannia.mosaic.virus

1500

1000

500

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Pandoravirus.salinus

300

200

100

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Klebsiella.virus.Matisse

400
300
200
100
0

0 100 200 300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Flavobacterium.phage.vB_FspS_laban6.1

200

100

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Moumouvirus

Potato.virus.S

Tomato.brown.rugose.fruit.virus

6e+06

4e+06

2e+06

0e+00

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Rhodobacter.virus.RcTitan

600
400
200
0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Pepper.mild.mottle.virus

9e+05

6e+05

3e+05

0e+00

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Melon.necrotic.spot.virus

60000

40000

20000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

